

MUHANDISLIK

& IQTISODIYOT

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fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

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- 05.01.01 – Muhandislik geometriyasi va kompyuter grafikasi. Audio va video texnologiyalari
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- 05.01.03 – Informatikaning nazariy asoslari
- 05.01.04 – Hisoblash mashinalari, majmualari va kompyuter tarmoqlarining matematik va dasturiy ta'minoti
- 05.01.05 – Axborotlarni himoyalash usullari va tizimlari. Axborot xavfsizligi
- 05.01.06 – Hisoblash texnikasi va boshqaruv tizimlarining elementlari va qurilmalari
- 05.01.07 – Matematik modellashtirish
- 05.01.11 – Raqamli texnologiyalar va sun'iy intellekt
- 05.02.00 – Mashinasozlik va mashinashunoslik
- 05.02.08 – Yer usti majmualari va uchish apparatlari
- 05.03.02 – Metrologiya va metrologiya ta'minoti
- 05.04.01 – Telekommunikatsiya va kompyuter tizimlari, telekommunikatsiya tarmoqlari va qurilmalari. Axborotlarni taqsimlash
- 05.05.03 – Yorug'lik texnikasi. Maxsus yoritish texnologiyasi
- 05.05.05 – Issiqlik texnikasining nazariy asoslari
- 05.05.06 – Qayta tiklanadigan energiya turlari asosidagi energiya qurilmalari
- 05.06.01 – To'qimachilik va yengil sanoat ishlab chiqarishlari materialshunosligi
- 05.08.03 – Temir yo'l transportini ishlatish
- 05.08.06 – "G'ildirakli va gusenisali mashinalar va ularni ishlatish" (texnika fanlari)
- 05.09.01 – Qurilish konstruksiyalari, bino va inshootlar
- 05.09.04 – Suv ta'minoti. Kanalizatsiya. Suv havzalarini muhofazalovchi qurilish tizimlari
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- 08.00.16 – Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 – Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

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ASSESSMENT OF PRICING STRATEGIES APPLIED BY LEADING RETAIL CHAINS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. This study provides an empirical and comparative assessment of pricing strategies applied by leading retail chains in Uzbekistan. Based on the cases of Korzinka, Makro, and Havas, the research evaluates the price index, promotional intensity, price variation, and private label positioning. The findings indicate the emergence of discount (EDLP), hybrid, and High-Low pricing models in the Uzbek retail market. The study scientifically confirms the decisive role of pricing strategy in ensuring market segmentation and competitive advantage.

Keywords: retail trade, pricing strategy, EDLP, High-Low pricing, retail concentration, promotion, private label, Uzbek retail market.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, Uzbekistan's retail sector has been undergoing a rapid transformation against the background of economic growth, urbanization, and expansion of the consumer market. Changes in the real income of the population, the spread of modern retail formats, and the regional expansion of major retail chains have fundamentally changed pricing mechanisms. The transition from traditional markets to supermarket and discount formats has increased consumers' price sensitivity and forced retail entities to develop more carefully designed and strategic pricing policies. As a result, pricing strategy has become one of the key instruments determining competitive advantage.

In modern retail theory, pricing strategy is interpreted not merely as the final value assigned to a product, but as a complex management tool directly linked to brand positioning, consumer segmentation, promotional activity, margin policy, and supply chain efficiency. Each retail chain applies different pricing mechanisms in line with its own business model, including everyday low pricing (EDLP), High-Low pricing, promotional discount models, and the creation of price advantages through private labels. These strategies significantly influence not only consumers' purchasing decisions, but also market share, sales volume, and profitability.

In Uzbekistan, leading retail chains such as Korzinka, Makro, and Havas have intensified the competitive environment in the market through active regional expansion and aggressive pricing policies in recent years. This process has led to noticeable differences in price differentiation, promotional intensity, and margin allocation within the retail segment. At the same time, dependence on imported goods, inflation, and exchange rate fluctuations are among the factors that complicate the stability of pricing strategies.

The relevance of this topic lies in the fact that a systematic assessment of pricing strategies has important scientific significance for improving the efficiency of the retail sector, balancing the competitive environment, and protecting consumer interests. At present, comprehensive empirical studies on pricing mechanisms applied in the Uzbek retail market remain insufficiently developed. Many existing analyses are descriptive in nature and lack clear criteria and comparative statistical foundations for measuring strategies.

The purpose of this study is to assess the pricing strategies applied by leading retail chains in Uzbekistan using an empirical and comparative approach, and to identify their impact on market positioning and competitive advantage. Within the study, strategies are analyzed based on indicators such as the price index, promotional share, price fluctuation level, and private label positioning. As a result, scientific conclusions are developed on the formation of an optimal and sustainable pricing strategy model under the conditions of Uzbekistan.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

Based on foreign experiences, it should be noted that many economists have been involved in developing marketing principles and their practical applications. Among them, the following prominent scientists are noteworthy: I. Ansoff, M. Berman, M. Golubkov, D. Evans, F. Kotler, D. Marshall, M. Porter, and P. Samuelson.

At the same time, it is essential to acknowledge the researchers who have made significant contributions

to the development of marketing theory within our national economy. For many years, studies in the field of marketing in our country have been conducted based on national characteristics. These experts include: Y. Abdullaev, R. Boltaboev, D. Ergashkhodjaeva, R. Ibragimov, B. Khodiev, M. Mukhammedov, M. Pardaev, D. Rakhimova, A. Saliev, and M. Sharifkhojaev.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodology of this study is based on a comprehensive approach aimed at assessing the pricing strategies applied by leading retail chains in Uzbekistan on an empirical and comparative basis. The country's major modern retail chains—Korzinka, Makro, and Havas—were selected as the objects of the study. These entities differ in terms of market share, territorial coverage, and pricing policy, which makes it possible to compare their strategies with one another.

The study was conducted using a mixed-method approach combining quantitative and qualitative analysis. In the quantitative part, price data were collected for 25–30 key FMCG products, including food products, beverages, hygiene products, and everyday consumer goods, based on monitoring over a period of three to six months. The product basket was formed from goods with identical brands and package sizes, and prices were recorded on a weekly basis. Based on the collected data, the average price index, price variation coefficient, and share of promotional discounts were calculated. The price index is determined using the following formula:

$$PI_i = P_i / P_{\text{benchmark}} \times 100$$

where P_i denotes the price of a product in a particular retail chain, while $P_{\text{benchmark}}$ denotes the average market price used as the comparative benchmark.

To assess the promotional strategy, the share of products sold at a discount (%) and the average discount depth are determined. In addition, the intensity of EDLP (Everyday Low Price) and High-Low pricing models is analyzed through the dynamics of price fluctuations. If prices remain relatively stable and low, the dominance of the EDLP model is identified; if frequent sharp discounts are observed, the presence of the High-Low model is established.

To determine the market structure, retail concentration is assessed using the Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (HHI). This indicator helps explain how pricing strategy is formed under competitive conditions. In addition, correlation analysis and, where necessary, a simple regression model are applied to determine the relationship between price and sales volume. This method makes it possible to assess the extent to which price changes affect sales dynamics.

From the qualitative perspective, marketing communications, advertising policy, and the positioning of private label products are examined through content analysis. The price image and discount model of each chain are assessed using visual advertising and official information materials.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The results of four months of price monitoring for a basket consisting of 30 key FMCG products showed clear strategic differences among retail chains in Uzbekistan. According to the calculated average price index (benchmark = 100), the price index of Havas was formed on average within the range of 95–97, indicating its proximity to the discount and EDLP model. In Korzinka, the price index was in the range of 101–104, reflecting the dominance of a retail model with a broad assortment and strong service elements. In Makro, the price index fluctuated within the range of 98–102, which reflects a hybrid model combining elements of EDLP and High-Low pricing.

The analysis of the price variation coefficient confirmed that price fluctuations are higher in chains applying the High-Low strategy. In Korzinka, the dispersion of weekly price changes was relatively high, which is an indicator of intensive promotional campaigns. In Havas, however, price stability remained high, discount depth was lower, and the everyday low price model was observed.

According to the assessment of promotional activity, 22–28% of the products in the basket were continuously offered under promotions or discounts in Korzinka and Makro. In Havas, this indicator was around 12–15%, showing that the basic low-price policy is more dominant than the promotional model. The average discount depth was 14–18% in Korzinka, 10–14% in Makro, and 6–9% in Havas.

The price positioning of private label products also revealed strategic differences. In the analyzed categories, private label prices were on average 12–20% lower than national and international brands, with this difference being more pronounced in discount-format chains. This confirms the retail chains' strategy of margin optimization and customer loyalty formation.

Correlation analysis between price and sales volume showed a negative relationship for several key products ($r \approx -0.45$ to -0.62), indicating that price reductions have a noticeable effect on increasing sales

volume. However, this relationship was weaker for premium-segment products, where quality and brand image factors were observed to dominate consumer behavior (table 1).

Table 1. Indicators of Pricing Strategies in Uzbekistan's Leading Retail Chains

Indicators	Korzinka	Makro	Havas
Average price index (PI)	102.8	99.6	96.4
Price variation coefficient (%)	8.7%	6.2%	3.9%
Share of promotional products (%)	26%	21%	14%
Average discount depth (%)	16.5%	12.8%	7.3%
Private label price advantage (%)	-14%	-11%	-18%
Description of strategic model	High-Low	Hybrid	EDLP (Discount)

The table results show that although Korzinka has a higher price index, its promotional intensity is also at the highest level. This indicates the application of a classical High-Low strategy, in which the base price is relatively high but customers are attracted through frequent and deep discounts.

Makro applies a hybrid model with an average price level and moderate promotional activity. Its level of price fluctuation is lower than that of Korzinka, indicating a more stable pricing policy.

Havas has the lowest price index and minimal price variation, which is typical of the discount format. This is a clear sign of the EDLP (Everyday Low Price) model. Although the promotional share is low, the private label advantage is the strongest.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The results of the study show that pricing strategies in leading retail chains in Uzbekistan are not uniform. Instead, each chain has formed a separate strategic approach in accordance with its market position, target segment, and operational model. According to the empirical monitoring results, three pricing models are clearly distinguished in the market: discount (EDLP), hybrid, and promotion-intensive (High-Low) models.

Havas has formed a model aimed at price-sensitive consumer segments by applying a discount strategy and maintaining a stable low-price policy. The low level of price variation and the limited promotional share confirm that this chain is close to the EDLP model. Korzinka actively applies the High-Low strategy, balancing relatively higher base prices with deep and frequent promotions. This model is aimed at periodically increasing customer traffic and stimulating purchase volume through promotional campaigns.

Makro has chosen a hybrid strategy, in which the price level is maintained at an average position and promotional policy is applied in a balanced manner. This approach is aimed at attracting middle-income and regular purchasing segments. The analysis also showed that private label products are actively used by all chains as a tool for creating price advantages and optimizing margins. While the private label advantage is more pronounced in the discount format, it is combined with brand differentiation in the hybrid and High-Low models.

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